

**The Alkaloids of *Holarrhena Antidysenterica*.
Part III. Studies in the Action of BrCN on
Conessine and its *N*-Demethylation to
*iso*Conessimine and Conimine.**

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The controversy which has till recently existed about the uniformity of conessine since its isolation by Haines as far back as 1858, is a measure of the confusion which has arisen through the sudden multiplication of the minor alkaloids of *Holarrhena antidysenterica* within the last few years, particularly when one takes into account the similarity between the analytical data and the physical properties of some of the 11 new bases isolated by the different authors (*cf.* Table, Siddiqui, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 286). The only possibility of effectively clearing up this confusion appeared to lie in the establishment of the exact nature of relationship between the different bases, especially in reference to conessine. The *N*-methylation of conessimine, *iso*conessimine and conimine to conessine (Siddiqui, *loc. cit.*) was the first and a definite step in this direction. The present paper mainly deals with a reversal of this process, namely the *N*-demethylation of conessine to *iso*conessimine and conimine by the saponification of the corresponding cyanamides, obtained through the action of BrCN on conessine and *cyanoiso*-conessimine respectively, after von Braun's general method of degrading tertiary to secondary amines, which was also used by him in obtaining the *N*-demethylated bases in the morphine series (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 3312)

A detailed study of the action of BrCN on conessine leads to the following conclusions in the light of von Braun's exhaustive investigations in the action of BrCN on tertiary amines on the one hand (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1279, and preceding papers) and Späth's formula for conessine on the other (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 126).

(1) That one of the two tertiary amino groups in the conessine molecule corresponds in its intensity of reaction to the type of the pure aliphatic amines, in so far as the monocyanamide is obtained in a quantitative yield immediately on bringing together the components in ethereal solution in the cold.

(2) The second tertiary amino group, very probably with the ring N, containing only one methyl, is comparatively very resistant against the action of BrCN, requiring about a week at room temperature for the completion of the reaction:

On the basis of these conclusions we feel justified in provisionally according the formula (I) for cyanoisocnessimine, (II) for isocnessimine, (III) for conessimine, (IV) for dicyanoconimine and (V) for conimine.

The fact that the monocyanamide (I) and the dicyanamide (IV) yielded on saponification bases whose mixed melting points, optical activities, analytical data proved them to be identical with isocnessimine and conimine respectively, finally dissolves every doubt about their purity. A full characterisation of isocnessimine and conimine, through their acetyl, benzoyl and nitroso derivatives which was postponed in Part II, has, therefore, been included in this paper. That no trace of cyanoconessimine was found to have been formed under the most varied experimental conditions for the BrCN reaction, agrees with the observation of von Braun that the action of BrCN is quantitatively in one direction and does not give rise to a mixture of cyanamides in case of bases containing only carbon and hydrogen in their molecule (*Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 3933).

was shaken with acetic acid and the acid fraction made alkaline with caustic soda without first boiling off the ether, when a white silky crystalline mass separated out, which after a single crystallisation from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether, yielded 11 g. of pure cyanoisoconessimine (yield theoretical).

The acetic acid-insoluble ethereal fraction gave just a trace of a treacle on removal of the solvent but no dicyanoconimine could be isolated from it. On refluxing 1 mol. of conessine (1.5 g.) with 2 mols. of BrCN (0.8 g.) in ethereal solution only 0.1 g. of dicyanoconimine could be isolated from the acid-insoluble and 0.4 g. cyanoisoconessimine from the acid-soluble ethereal fraction. Substitution of chloroform for ether as a solvent for this reaction lowered the yields of both cyanoisoconessimine and dicyanoconimine, their mother liquors yielding undefinable reddish treacly products. When 1 mol. (21 g.) of conessine was refluxed with only 1 mol. (6.3 g.) of BrCN in chloroform solution for an hour and the reaction mixture worked up in the general sense of the method given above, 3.5 g. of cyanoisoconessimine, 0.8 g. of dicyanoconimine, 8 g. of conessine dimethoxybromide and (on fractional crystallisation of the residue from the mother liquors of the quaternary ammonium compound from ethyl acetate) 2.5 g. of conessine monohydrobromide were obtained.

Action of BrCN on cyanoisoconessimine.—Attempts to obtain a satisfactory yield of dicyanoconimine through the direct action of BrCN on conessine having failed, the action of BrCN on cyanoisoconessimine was tried in different solvents under varying conditions. The only method that gave quantitative results was the following.

2 G. of cyanoisoconessimine were dissolved in 20 c.c. of dry ethyl acetate, a solution of 0.6 g. BrCN in 10 c.c. ethyl acetate added to it and the mixture kept well corked at room temperature. After a few hours clusters and stars of large spike-formed amber-coloured crystals of cyanoisoconessimine methobromide, m. p. 255°, began to separate out. (Found: N, 8.69; Br, 16.73. $C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot CN \cdot CH_3Br$ requires N, 9.09; Br, 17.3 per cent). After a week the ethyl acetate solution was filtered off from the crystalline mass (0.35 g.), the filtrate shaken with acetic acid for the removal of traces of unreacted cyanoisoconessimine, washed with dilute alkali and dried over sodium sulphate. On crystallising the colourless treacle, left on removal of the solvent, from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether, 1 g. of pure dicyanoconimine was obtained.

Characterisation of the Products of BrCN Reaction.

Cyanoisoconessimine.—It is easily soluble in alcohol, chloroform and benzene, less so in ethyl acetate and acetone, difficultly soluble in ether and insoluble in petroleum ether. It crystallises from absolute alcohol, in which it is not very easily soluble, in elongated plates with angular edges, and from ether and ethyl acetate in plates (m.p. 182-83°). Having only one basic N, it is monoacidic and rectangular forms a single series of salts. [Found: N, 11·09; CH₃, 8·09. C₂₃H₃₇N₂·CN requires N, 11·18; (for 2N·CH₃) CH₃, 8·17 per cent].

The hydrochloride was obtained by adding ether to a solution of the base in alcoholic HCl as an oil which crystallised from a mixture of alcohol, ether and petroleum ether in clusters of tapering needles melting at 289-90° (decomp.). It is easily soluble in alcohol, fairly so in hot water, acetone and insoluble in ether. (Found: Cl, 9·09. C₂₃H₃₇N₂·CN, HCl requires Cl, 8·79 per cent).

The chloroplatinate was obtained by adding a solution of platinic chloride to the aqueous solution of the hydrochloride as a golden yellow powder, insoluble in water but fairly soluble in hot methyl alcohol from which it crystallised out on slow cooling in tufts of slender needles, m. p. 210-11° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 17·53. (C₂₃H₃₇N₂·CN·HCl)₂·PtCl₄ requires Pt, 17·07 per cent].

The picrate was obtained by adding ethereal solution of picric acid to a solution of the base in methyl alcohol as an oily treacle, turning into a bright yellow microcrystalline powder (m.p. 139-40°) on rubbing with hot water. It is easily soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl acetate and acetone, difficultly soluble in absolute alcohol or water and insoluble in ether.

Dicyanoconimine.—Its solubility in different organic solvents is very similar in character to that of cyanoisoconessimine. It crystallises from ether, ethyl acetate and acetone, also from concentrated solutions of absolute alcohol in elongated plates with angular edges and melts at 159-60°. Being neutral in character, it does not form any salts and is insoluble in acids and alkalis. [Found: N, 13·47; CH₃, 4·11. C₂₂H₃₄N₂(CN)₂ requires N, 14·66; (for 1N·CH₃) CH₃, 3·93 per cent].

Conessine dimethobromide.—It crystallises from a mixture of alcohol and ethyl acetate in prismatic rods and plates which melt at 321-22° (decomp.). It is easily soluble in alcohol, chloroform and

water. From its aqueous solution it separates on addition of caustic soda in woolly flakes and can be shaken out with chloroform [Found: N, 5.08; Br, 29.6; CH₃, 14.3. C₂₄H₄₀N₂(CH₃Br)₂ requires N, 5.13; Br, 29.3; (for 5N-CH₃) CH₃, 13.7 per cent].

Conessine monohydrobromide.—It is easily soluble in alcohol and water and difficultly soluble in acetone and ethyl acetate, from which it crystallises in prismatic rods melting at 310-11° (decomp.). [Found: CH₃, 11.0; Br, 19.0. C₂₄H₄₀N₂, HBr requires (for 3 CH₃) CH₃, 10.3; Br, 18.3 per cent].

Saponification of cyanoisoconessimine.—5 G. of cyanoisoconessimine in 50 c.c. of 20% absolute alcoholic potash were refluxed on the water-bath for 48 hours, in the course of which a crystalline mass slowly separated out, which was identified as potassium carbonate. The slightly reddish residue left on removal of the major portion of alcohol was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution washed with water and then shaken with acetic acid. The nearly colourless, acidic solution was made alkaline with caustic soda and shaken with ether. On removal of the solvent from the well dried ethereal solution, a colourless treacle was obtained, which crystallised from ethyl acetate in clusters and stars of needles melting at 92°, yield 4 g. On admixture with isoconessimine from the bark, it did not show any depression in its melting point. With conessimine it began to soften at 70° and completely melted at 80°. In agreement with isoconessimine from the plant it showed a rotation, $[\alpha]_D^{28} = +30^\circ$ in 1% absolute alcohol solution.

Derivatives of isoConessimine.

Benzoylisoconessimine.—0.3 G. of isoconessimine was finely powdered with 0.12 g. of benzoic anhydride and the mixture which melted at 55° was slowly heated in a sulphuric acid bath up to 140°. After cooling the hard slightly reddish molten mass was dissolved in acetic acid, the acidic solution made alkaline with caustic soda and shaken with ether. The treacle left on removal of the solvent from the dried ethereal solution was taken up in petroleum ether, treated with moist carbon dioxide to remove traces of unreacted base and the colourless solution dried over potassium carbonate. The treacle left on distilling off the solvent yielded the benzoyl base on crystallisation from acetone in aggregates of elongated plates, m.p. 159-60°, yield 0.2 g. It is soluble in alcohol and ethyl acetate,

slightly less so in acetone, ether and petroleum ether and is a mono-acidic base in character. (Found: C, 79.5; H, 9.35; N, 6.16. $C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot CO \cdot C_6H_5$ requires C, 80.7; H, 9.42; N, 6.28 per cent).

The hydrochloride was obtained as a crystalline powder, easily soluble in alcohol, water and acetone by adding ethereal hydrochloric acid to an ethereal solution of the base, m.p. 325-26° (decomp.).

The chloroplatinate was obtained by adding 10% platinum chloride solution to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride as an amber coloured powder, difficultly soluble in alcohol and insoluble in water, m.p. 264-65° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 18.5. $(C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot CO \cdot C_6H_5, HCl) 1\frac{1}{2} PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 18.4 per cent].

Acetylisococonessimine.—0.25 G. of isoconessimine hydrochloride and 0.5 g. of sodium acetate were dissolved in 2 c.c. water and 0.6 g. of acetic anhydride added to the solution, which was then heated on the water-bath for an hour. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water, made alkaline with caustic soda and shaken with ether. The residue from the ethereal solution was taken up in petroleum ether and treated with moist carbon dioxide to remove any unreacted base, when a little brownish scum separated out. The colourless solution was dried over potassium carbonate and the filtrate concentrated, when the pure acetyl base separated out in aggregates of rectangular plates, yield 0.15 g. melting at 127-28° and easily soluble in alcohol, ethyl acetate, acetone and ether, less so in petroleum ether. (Found: C, 78.32; H, 10.66; N, 7.65. $C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot CO \cdot CH_3$ requires C, 78.1; H, 10.4; N, 7.29 per cent).

The hydrochloride was obtained by adding ethereal hydrochloric acid to an ethereal solution of the base as a white microcrystalline powder which is soluble in alcohol and water and melts at 325-26° (decomp.). Acetylisococonessimine hydrochloride as prepared by adding an ethereal solution of acetyl chloride to an ether solution of isoconessimine also melted at 325-26°. (Found: Cl, 9.58. $C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot CO \cdot CH_3, HCl$ requires Cl, 8.64 per cent).

The chloroplatinate was obtained by adding 5% platinum chloride solution to the aqueous solution of the hydrochloride as an amber coloured powder, which shrinks at 246° and melts at 265-66° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 21.02. $(C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot CO \cdot CH_3, HCl) 1\frac{1}{2} PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 20.2 per cent].

Thus both benzoyl and acetylisococonessimines agree with acetylconessemine (Part II, *loc. cit.*) in forming chloroplatinates answering to the type $(B, HCl) 1\frac{1}{2}PtCl_4$.

Nitrosoisoconessimine.—A concentrated solution of sodium nitrite was added in drops to a cooled solution of the base (0.2 g.) in acetic acid with constant stirring. The white granular precipitate was washed with a little water and dissolved in excess of acetic acid, the base liberated with caustic soda and extracted with petroleum ether. On drying the solution over potassium carbonate and concentrating the filtrate, nitrosoisoconessimine crystallised out in the cold in spike-formed amber coloured needles, m. p. 163-64°, yield 0.12 g. It is soluble in ether, alcohol and acetone, difficultly soluble in petroleum ether and behaves as a monoacidic base. (Found: C, 74.71; H, 10.08; N, 10.94. $C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot NO$ requires C, 74.4; H, 9.97; N, 11.3 per cent).

The hydrochloride, prepared from the components in ethereal solution, formed a crystalline powder which is soluble in alcohol and water and melts at 248-51° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 9.33. $C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot NO$, HCl requires Cl, 8.92 per cent).

The picrate was obtained from the components in ethereal solution as a bright yellow powder, which crystallised from methyl alcohol in clusters of lemon-yellow tapering needles, which are difficultly soluble in cold, fairly in hot water or alcohol and melt at 190-94°.

Saponification of Dicyanoconimine: Conimine.

2.2 G. of dicyanoconimine was refluxed with 20% absolute alcoholic caustic potash solution (40 c.c.) for 12 hours, when crystals of potassium carbonate slowly separated out. The reddish residue left on removal of the alcohol was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water and shaken with dilute acetic acid, from which the base was liberated with caustic soda and extracted with ether. The pale treacly residue, left on removing the solvent from the dried ethereal solution, crystallised from ethyl acetate in clusters and stars of spike-formed needles, yield 1.3 g. It melted at 134° and showed no depression in its m. p. on admixture with conimine from the plant. The melting points of the hydrochloride and the picrate of the base also concurred with those of conimine. It showed a rotation $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -30^\circ$ in 1% solution in absolute alcohol.

Derivatives of Conimine.

Dibenzoylconimine.—To a solution of 0.5 g. of conimine in 3 c.c. pyridine was added 0.5 g. of benzoyl chloride in a little ether with

cooling and the reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 3 hours. On dilution with water clusters of spindle shaped needles were obtained, which on recrystallisation from chloroform and acetone melted at 250° . It is easily soluble in chloroform, alcohol and ethyl acetate, difficulty soluble in acetone and insoluble in ether and petroleum ether. [Found: C, 79.41; H, 8.23; N, 5.31. $C_{22}H_{34}N_2$ ($CO \cdot C_6H_5$)₂ requires C, 80.60; H, 8.21; N, 5.22 per cent].

Diacetylconimine.—An intimate mixture of conimine (0.5 g), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) and acetic anhydride (1 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for 3 hours. The reaction mixture on dilution with water gave a treacly residue which was extracted with ethyl acetate and dried over sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent the colourless residue was dried in vacuo over P_2O_5 when a semicrystalline snow white powder (0.4 g.) was obtained, which was soluble in hot petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, alcohol and chloroform, insoluble in ether and melted at 139.40° . [Found: C, 75.67; H, 9.79; N, 6.75. $C_{22}H_{34}N_2$ ($CO \cdot CH_3$)₂ requires C, 75.72; H, 9.71; N, 6.79 per cent].

Dinitrosoconimine.—A concentrated solution of sodium nitrite was added in drops to 1 g. of conimine in 5 c.c. of 10% acetic acid with good cooling and stirring. On keeping the mixture for 1 hour at room temperature a viscous oil separated which turned into a powder on rubbing and washing with acetic acid and then with water. On concentrating a solution of the powder in acetone, nitrosoconimine was obtained in aggregates of rectangular plates (0.9 g.) melting at 206.07° . It also crystallises from alcohol or benzene. It is easily soluble in acetone, ethyl acetate, benzene, chloroform and alcohol and insoluble in ether, petroleum ether and water. [Found: N, 14.17. $C_{22}H_{34}N_2$ (NO)₂ requires N, 14.5 per cent].

